

INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION ISRAEL- EUROPE IN THE FIELD OF CLIMATE PROTECTION

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Abstract: *The effects of climate change and rapid population growth pose a threat to global food production by increasing water demand on the one hand and water scarcity on the other. Recognizing the interconnected nature of agricultural systems is essential to understanding the amplification or attenuation of risks through social processes and responses that are often lacking from modelling and risk assessments, particularly in terms of multiple use and re-use of water for food production. Interactions across sectors and countries, particularly those involving food, water, and ecosystem services are an important determinant of climate change impacts. There is cooperation between Europe Union and other countries, especially in the Mediterranean region, including Israel. This paper describes an AWESOME project as an example of such a cooperation which aims at addressing this challenge and advancing the state-of-the-art with innovative contributions in relation to the various underpinning disciplinary approaches adopted by the research.*

Key words: *WEF- water-ecosystem-food Nexus; Mediterranean region; AWESOME - mAnaging Water, Ecosystems and food across sectors and Scales in the sOuth Mediterranean; Europe Union.*

МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЕ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВО ИЗРАИЛЬ-ЕВРОПА В ОБЛАСТИ ЗАЩИТЫ КЛИМАТА

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Аннотация: *Последствия изменения климата и быстрого роста населения представляют угрозу мировому производству продуктов питания из-за увеличения спроса на воду, с одной стороны, и дефицита воды — с другой. Признание взаимосвязанного характера сельскохозяйственных систем имеет важное значение для понимания усиления или ослабления рисков через социальные процессы и*

ответные меры, которые часто отсутствуют в моделировании и оценке рисков, особенно с точки зрения многократного использования и повторного использования воды для производства продуктов питания. Взаимодействие между секторами и странами, особенно те, которые связаны с продовольствием, водой и экосистемными услугами, являются важным фактором, определяющим последствия изменения климата. Существует сотрудничество между Европейским Союзом и другими странами, особенно в Средиземноморском регионе, включая Израиль. В этом документе проект AWESOME описывается как пример такого сотрудничества, которое направлено на решение этой проблемы и продвижение новейшего уровня техники за счет инновационного вклада в отношении различных основополагающих дисциплинарных подходов, принятых в исследовании.

Ключевые слова: ВЭП – связь «вода-экосистема-продовольствие»; Средиземноморский регион; AWESOME – управление водными ресурсами, экосистемами и продовольствием в различных секторах и масштабах Южного Средиземноморья; Европейский Союз.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing global population and economic prosperity are projected to drive the demand for energy, food, and water in Mediterranean regions. However, this growing demand may jeopardize the sustainable use of natural resources by overemphasizing economic and societal benefits while underestimating the negative impact on essential ecosystem services [2]. As climate change continues to reduce the availability of natural freshwater sources, alternative water sources will become crucial in water-stressed countries within the Mediterranean region [9]. Therefore, it is imperative to explore strategies that enable the production of more food while minimizing water, land, and energy consumption. Achieving this balance is essential to address the interconnectedness of the water, ecosystem, and food systems (referred to as the WEF Nexus). Recognizing the Mediterranean as a valuable natural capital that offers significant but often undervalued ecosystem services, it becomes essential to adopt transformative approaches to natural resource management. These approaches should integrate and involve multiple stakeholders, considering the interconnectedness of the water, ecosystem, and food systems (WEF Nexus). Both public and private actors should actively participate in these efforts to ensure a more sustainable use of natural resources, leading to long-term food and environmental security. To achieve this, collaboration with various stakeholders such as local businesses, administrators, NGOs, and community members is crucial. Mediterranean countries should focus on developing economically, technically, and institutionally feasible WEF innovations, including practical business solutions and policy recommendations. Additionally, it is

important to identify the existing and potential barriers that hinder the implementation of these innovations and suggest strategies to overcome them.

Furthermore, emphasizing a strong policy orientation in collaborative projects and involving key stakeholders will promote synergies among actors and facilitate the development of sustainable institutional approaches at different levels of governance. By adopting such approaches, the Mediterranean region can effectively address the challenges of resource management and contribute to the overall sustainability and well-being of the region.

International cooperation in the Mediterranean region

The Europe Union is leading in solving climate issues. The Green Deal ambitious program of Europe Union strives to reduce green gas emissions, and its objectives are to reach 55% reduction by the end of this decade and full balance in 50 years [3]. As of now, Israel is not a central player like India, China, USA and Europe. However, Israel may contribute a lot in innovations. Israeli economic is based on innovations and enterprise. Israeli scientists develop models assessing the economic value of seawater desalination, a major service provided by the Mediterranean, which stabilizes the water supply and diminishes the effects of natural freshwater shortages [7; 8]. Cooperation in the fields of climate change and innovations are very valuable.

There are plenty of international organizations in the Mediterranean region who work together on solving climate issues, including Israeli academic and business organizations. Actively collaborating with stakeholders including local businesses, administrators, NGOs, and community members, international cooperation will produce feasible (economically, technically and institutionally) WEF innovations in the form of effective business solutions and policy recommendations and, at the same time, it will also identify perceived and potential barriers to nurturing these WEF innovations, and recommend avenues to overcome them.

AWESOME as effective international cooperation

AWESOME - mAnaging Water, Ecosystems and food across sectors and Scales in the sOuth MEditerranean is developing a decision-analytic platform based on a multi-level, integrated WEF model to better understand multi-sectoral WEF tradeoffs and to capitalize on potential synergies, also exploring the interdependencies and feedbacks across a hierarchy of spatial scales, from the macroeconomic development of the Mediterranean region and national scale, to regional planning at river basin scale, down to the single farm. The platform will provide a simulation capability to assess the impacts of different WEF planning

portfolios. These portfolios will consist of regional policies, river-basin strategic planning options, and innovative technological solutions that have been successfully demonstrated at the local scale. The aim is to generate shared economic, environmental, and societal benefits by exploring various combinations of these strategies.

Through a model-based assessment, the platform will facilitate the discovery of solutions that enhance the resilience of the agricultural sector. It will promote the sustainable use of natural resources and ensure long-term food security, particularly in the face of changing climate patterns and societal dynamics that lead to variations in water availability and demand.

The integration of models running at different spatial scales - micro, meso and macro - allow (1) a better characterization of different, innovative technological solutions demonstrated at the micro-scale to produce more crop per drop [6] , namely soilless agriculture (hydroponics), aquaculture, and the integration of soilless agriculture and aquaculture (aquaponics) potentially supported by solar energy and desalination plants, for informing strategic planning at the meso (river basin) scale; (2) a more realistic representation of macro-scale processes and regional policies influencing river basin dynamics in terms of land use, water and energy demands, and ecosystem services.

The three level-nature of the platform (micro-meso-macro) will support both the generation of realistic projections at the local scale driven by global trends associated to changing climate and society as modelled at the macro scale, as well as the identification of candidate WEF portfolios and their successful uptake as demonstrated at the micro-scale. The direct involvement of a broad range of relevant stakeholders in different phases of the project activities will ensure the relevance and uptake of the project outputs. Collected feedbacks will be used to extensively analyse the portability of the AWESOME platform to other Mediterranean contexts.

AWESOME has the following concrete objectives and key deliverables:

- AWESOME seeks to provide a better understanding of the tradeoffs, synergies, and nested interdependencies that exist within the components of the WEF Nexus across different spatial scales. The project aims to analyze these dynamics at various levels, ranging from the whole Mediterranean region to river basin scales, and down to the farm scale. By doing so, AWESOME aims to uncover the complex relationships and interactions among water, energy, and food systems, taking into account their interconnections and interdependencies;

- a better characterization of opportunities and constraints to the implementation and successful uptake of multi-sectoral WEF portfolios aimed at

improving agricultural and environmental sustainability, explicitly accounting for local stakeholders and global events/policies;

- improved WEF portfolios aimed at increasing the resilience of the agricultural sector supported by deep engagement with relevant stakeholders including farmers, local business representatives, public authorities, NGOs, policy makers, and citizens;

- To maximize the project's impact, AWESOME will prioritize the dissemination of knowledge and actively promote dialogue, learning, and understanding among different sectors, policy makers, and stakeholders. By fostering collaboration and information sharing, the project aims to create a platform for exchange, enabling stakeholders to benefit from each other's expertise, experiences, and perspectives.

- Through various dissemination activities, AWESOME will ensure that project findings, insights, and recommendations reach a wide audience [5].

AWESOME's consortium consists of a highly international and interdisciplinary partnership, which includes 6 academic and research institutions and 1 SME, and covers all the technical-engineering and socio-economic knowledge domains required by the proposed integrated approach. Partners are fairly distributed across the Mediterranean, with 3 partners from the North Mediterranean and 3 from the South, and the German partner with strong linkages with the case study context. From the academic qualification point of view, the consortium has a significant potential to produce relevant scientific innovations as the partners have an excellent academic record both in research and teaching in the water, food and ecosystems domains of AWESOME. Publications, research achievement and past projects cover well the wide range of disciplines required to develop the AWESOME platform. Yet AWESOME will contribute not only to research and innovation, but will also provide key links to local knowledge, socio-economic development cultures, policy institution and implementation bodies by bridging the project with relevant local stakeholders, policy makers, and authorities.

AWESOME recognizes the importance of disseminating scientific knowledge and policy recommendations to the international scientific community, policy makers, and relevant stakeholders. The project will utilize conferences and scientific journals as the primary channels for sharing the scientific knowledge generated by AWESOME with the global scientific community. Through these platforms, researchers will present their findings, methodologies, and insights, contributing to the body of knowledge on the WEF Nexus in the Mediterranean region.

In addition to conferences and scientific journals, AWESOME will develop policy briefs and position papers specifically tailored for policy makers. These

documents will provide concise and targeted summaries of the project's key findings and policy recommendations. By distilling complex research into accessible formats, AWESOME aims to effectively communicate relevant information to policymakers, supporting evidence-based decision-making processes.

To facilitate the transfer and exploitation of project results, AWESOME will produce solutions transferability and portability reports. These reports will provide in-depth analyses of the challenges and opportunities associated with applying the AWESOME framework, results, and lessons learned beyond the project's case study area to other basins in the Mediterranean region. By identifying transferability aspects, the reports will guide the replication and adaptation of AWESOME's approaches and solutions in different contexts.

AWESOME will also organize a training module in the form of a Summer School, supplemented by online training materials. This module will aim to transfer and disseminate project results to young professionals, including students, practitioners, and policy makers, from both European and Mediterranean regions. The training materials will be made available online, ensuring accessibility and broad dissemination to reach the widest possible audience.

By employing a diverse range of dissemination strategies, including scientific channels, policy briefs, position papers, transferability reports, and training modules, AWESOME aims to maximize its impact and effectively reach the relevant stakeholders. Through these efforts, the project aims to contribute to the advancement of knowledge, inform policy decisions, and foster capacity building in the field of the WEF Nexus in the Mediterranean region.

SUMMARY

The effects of climate change and rapid population growth present significant challenges to global food production, as they lead to increased water demand and water scarcity. It is crucial to recognize the interconnected nature of agricultural systems to fully understand how risks are amplified or mitigated through social processes and responses [4]. Unfortunately, many modeling and risk assessment approaches often overlook these social dimensions and the complexities associated with the multiple uses and re-use of water in food production [1].

The interactions across sectors and countries, particularly those involving food, water, and ecosystem services, play a crucial role in determining the impacts of climate change. These interactions occur within and between multiple sectors and spatial dimensions, making the transmission pathways of climate change impacts complex.

The interconnectedness of these sectors and countries means that changes in one area can have ripple effects and consequences in others. For example, changes in precipitation patterns can affect agricultural productivity, leading to shifts in food production and availability. These changes in turn can impact food security, trade patterns, and economic stability both locally and globally. There is cooperation between Europe Union and other countries, especially in the Mediterranean region, including Israel. The importance of capturing such interconnections is increasingly apparent, and the multi-sector and multi-scale design of AWESOME project as an example of such a cooperation that aims at addressing this challenge and advancing the state-of-the-art with innovative contributions in relation to the various underpinning disciplinary approaches adopted by the research.

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